

Workshop #2 Background and Agenda

Human health risk assessment frameworks for micro- and nanoplastics

Tuesday, March 14, 2023, 12:30 pm - 17:00 pm (CET)

Assessing the human health effects of micro- and nanoplastics (MNPs) is challenging for several reasons. MNPs are complex mixtures. MNPs may have different geometries, shapes and sizes. They can be made from different polymer types and contain various additives and contaminants.

This workshop was the second in a three-part series on the human risk assessment of micro- and nanoplastics (MNPs) organised by [CUSP Working Group on Risk Assessment \(WG5\)](#) and CUSP member projects.

Workshop 1 was organized by WG5 and PlasticHeal on February 7th and focused on regulatory insights and knowledge gaps.

Workshop 2 was organised by WG5 and Polyrisk on March 14th and focused on risk assessment frameworks on March 14th and organized by WG5 and POLYRISK.

Workshop 3 was organized by WG5 and PlasticsFatE on April 21st and focused on data and information gaps.

About the Second Workshop

The workshop attracted over 150 participants and engendered stimulating discussions on how to establish frameworks for assessing human health risks of MNPs. The first session provided an overview of existing approaches and frameworks for polymers and nanomaterials, which might be relevant for MNPs. The second session saw discussions on how the existing approaches and frameworks can be adapted for MNPs.

Participants were invited to actively engage in the scientific discussions during the breakout sessions. Some of the questions to be tackled included: 'How useful are the existing frameworks for MNPs?' and 'Where should we set priorities for research in the next few years?'

CUSP thematic workshop series Human Risk Assessment of MNPs

Register here: <https://bit.ly/3YAJtEV>

Workshop #2/3

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Agenda

12:30 **Welcome and introduction**
POLYRISK

I. Existing concepts and frameworks for polymers and nanomaterials

Chair: Dirk Brossell (BAuA, POLYRISK)

12:40 **Risk assessment of polymers - the perspective of EU REACH**
Oliver Peters, BAuA, Germany (POLYRISK)

13:00 **Risk assessment of nanomaterials - overview on existing frameworks**
Steffen Foss Hansen, DTU, Denmark (PlasticHeal)

13:20 **Q&A and discussion**

II. Adapting the existing concepts and frameworks for MNPs

Chair: Raymond Pieters (Utrecht University, POLYRISK)

13:30 **Towards an integrated approach for testing and assessment for poorly soluble, low toxicity polymer particles**
Annie Jarabek, US EPA

13:50 **Are existing frameworks for nanomaterials useful for MNPs?**
Matthew Boyles, IOM, UK (AURORA) (TBC)

14:20 **The POLYRISK Risk Assessment Framework for MNPs**
Andrea Haase, BfR, Germany (POLYRISK)

14:40 **Q&A and discussion**

15:00 **Coffee break**

III. Interactive discussion

15:30 **Break-out sessions**

16:30 **Concluding remarks and outlook**